

Geophysical Imaging of Frictional Contacts and Processes in Shaly Sandstone Rock Joints

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ABSTRACT: We use a direct shear apparatus with embedded ultrasonic transducers to correlate the macroscopic frictional response with the microscopic contact processes occurring between two blocks of shaly sandstone. At constant normal load, we observe stable sliding at low velocities and oscillatory stick-slip at high velocities. For slow sliding, or during the stick phase of the stick-slip cycle, variations in the transmitted compressional P-wave amplitude show the existence of healing processes occurring at the joint, e.g. associated to the increase in contact area with contact time. Moreover, the transmitted shear S-wave amplitude is sensitive to other processes with opposite velocity dependence. The interplay between these processes, displaying velocity weakening (VW) and velocity strengthening (VS) respectively, explain the observed maximum in the steady state shear response as function of shearing rate. We also observe that the wave velocity is sensitive to gouge formation at the joint. This mechanism is induced by sliding and enhanced with shearing rate. At low shearing rates, in the VS region, small amounts of debris are formed, slightly strengthening the joint. At high shearing rates, in the VW region, the wear material significantly increases the mean separation between the two surfaces, resulting in a weaker joint.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding contact scale physical processes is necessary to interpret in detail the frictional behavior of natural and simulated faults. The extent of these processes, such as plastic creep, gouge comminution or capillary condensation, directly determine the state of contact and overall strength of the fault, either by affecting the real contact area or the local strength of contact zones. Geophysical imaging of ultrasonic waves interacting with rock joints have been used as a non-destructive technique that measures the state of contact and real contact area (Kendall and Tabor, 1971; Nagata et al., 2008, 2012; Hedayat, 2013; Hedayat et al., 2014a-d; Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a). Ultrasonic waves transmit through the points in contact and reflect at the air void spaces and in this way they can provide an indirect measure of the state of contact within the zone of measurement. Thus, the intensity of the wave transmitted through the asperities in contact can be a measure of the stiffness of the asperities and the real contact area.

Shear experiments conducted on gypsum rock joints (Hedayat et al., 2012; 2013) and Indiana limestone rock joints (Hedayat et al., 2014a, 2018; Hedayat and Walton, 2017) show that precursors in the form of

maximum amplitude of ultrasonic waves appear before reaching the static shear strength of contacting surfaces. Based on the variations in the amplitude of transmitted and reflected ultrasonic waves, Hedayat et al. (2018) identified two major processes occurring during both frictional sliding and stick-slip oscillations, as follows: (a) interseismic phase and (b) preseismic phase. The interseismic phase was associated with small local slip rate and increasing ultrasonic transmission along the contact surfaces while the rock joint was locked. Such increase in the ultrasonic transmission represented an increase in the real (true) area of contact. The onset of preseismic phase was associated with the appearance of precursors for different regions of the rock joint.

Quantification of the elastic properties during shearing by measuring ultrasonic wave speed across either the bare rock surfaces or the gouge layers is now common. Examples of such work include Nagata et al., 2012; Scuderi et al., 2016; and Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a. However, the majority of research work utilizes a single pair of transducer that can only monitor a small portion of the laboratory rock joint and fault and therefore the spatial variations across the length of the fault is typically left unexplored. Associating the local changes by measuring the wave attributes (e.g. peak-

to-peak amplitude, wave velocity and dominant frequency) from a single isolated area with the global shear properties such as shear stress, slip velocity, slip amount is often challenging and results in no clear conclusion. In this research, we utilized a series of compressional and shear transducers to monitor not only the local evolution of the fault's normal and shear stiffness and the contact area but also their spatial variations.

We also address the effect of gouge generation during sliding, which to our knowledge, has not been studied with acoustic transmission. In a high velocity regime, at and below flash heating sliding, Yamashita et al., 2014 observe fault strengthening at sub-seismic velocities and fault weakening at seismic velocities. They explain this behavior with a model of gouge formation during sliding. These observations are analog to ours, though in a much higher velocity regime.

2. LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

A series of direct shear experiments were conducted on a rock joint (interface) made of Gosford sandstone (a shaly rock) and nine pairs of source-receiver transducers were placed at the sides of the specimen to simultaneously record changes in the ultrasonic compressional, P- and shear, S- wave attributes (peak-to-peak amplitude and wave velocity). This section first describes the specimen's properties and preparation and then the experimental setup.

Fig. 1. Location map Triassic series

2.1. Sample Properties and Preparation

Gosford sandstone samples were sourced from Gosford Quarry, Somersby, New South Wales, Australia. Gosford sandstone forms a unit within the massive (290 m thick) Triassic Hawkesbury sandstone of the Sydney Basin (Ord et al., 1991) on the east coast of New South Wales, Australia. The unit occupies

some 800 km² of the Sydney Basin (see Figure 1) and is typically composed of sub-angular to sub-rounded quartz grain, with argillaceous matrix, minor feldspar and clay (Ord et al., 1991).

Some earlier studies have investigated this rock under different testing conditions including uniaxial compression (Masoumi et al., 2014; Masoumi et al., 2016; Roshan et al., 2016; Masoumi et al., 2017), triaxial compression (Masoumi et al., 2016; Masoumi et al., 2017; Roshan et al., 2017), and indirect tensile and point load testing (Forbes et al., 2015; Masoumi et al., 2018). Homogenous core samples were carefully selected with no macro-scale defects. The porosity of Gosford sandstone has been measured by Roshan et al., 2016, 2018 using X-ray CT scanning technique at about 20%. Masoumi et al., 2016 conducted X-ray diffraction on the same batch of Gosford sandstone utilized in this study which includes 86 % quartz, 7 % illite, 6 % kaolinite and 1% anatase. The reported maximum grain size of this sandstone was 0.6 mm.

According to Masoumi et al., 2016, the Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) of Gosford sandstone with diameter of 50 mm and length/diameter ration of 2 is about 52.3 MPa. For the same size, Masoumi, 2013 reported the average Young's Modulus (E) and Poisson's ratio of Gosford sandstone at 12.1 GPa and 0.14, respectively.

Each sample was 101.6 mm (4 inch) long, 101.6 mm (4 inch) wide, and approximately 50.4 mm (2 inch) thick. The specimens were oven-dried at temperature 90 °C for 24 hrs to remove any residual moisture. Figure 2 shows the fractured sandstone specimen that was used for direct shear testing.

Fig. 2. Gosford sandstone rock joint

2.2. Experimental setup

To measure the coupled mechanical-geophysical behavior of rock joints, we utilized an instrumented direct shear apparatus with an ultrasonic imaging system. The following sections describe the details of the equipment used.

(a) Direct Shear Apparatus

Figure 3 contains a photograph of the direct shear apparatus used to perform shear tests on rock joints. The apparatus consists of two independent devices: (a) a horizontal loading frame to control the confining

pressure and (b) a vertical loading machine to control the shear load.

The horizontal loading frame consists of a flatjack, loading platens that encase a specimen and seismic transducers. A flatjack (ENERPAC RSM-500) was used to apply a constant normal (confining) pressure during the experiment and was connected to a hydraulic pump with a closed loop servo-valve system. The system allowed to maintain the desired confining pressure constant throughout the experiment.

A loading machine with 1 Million lb capacity in the vertical direction was used to impose the shearing velocities on the top of the specimen. The shear load was applied at various displacement rates of the top platen of the loading machine. Three linear variable displacement transducers (LVDTs), placed on top of the loading platen, measured the vertical (shear) displacement of the specimen and provided input to the servo-controlled loading machine for the application of shear displacement. One LVDT was also used for the measurement of the average normal displacement (i.e., horizontal displacement in Figure 3). A special lubricant (Moly Anti-Seize) was used between the loading platen and the horizontal loading frame to eliminate any friction between the two well-polished stainless steel surfaces. This was done to ensure that the vertical load was resisted solely by the rock joint interface between the blocks and not by the friction in the experimental setup.

Fig. 3. Direct Shear Test Set up.

(b) Ultrasonic Measurement System

Full-waveform compressional, P- and shear, S- waves were transmitted across the rock joint during the shearing test. Nine pairs of wave transducers were placed on each side of the joint, as shown in Figure 3. The transducers were housed inside the specially designed loading platens on each side of the rock block (right and left in Figure 3). Figure 4 shows

schematically the transducer layout that was used for seismic measurements.

During the experiments, the interface between the two blocks in contact was constantly monitored by measuring full waveform P- and S- waves transmitted through the rock joint. Each source and receiver platen contained 4 shear wave transducers that were polarized in the direction of shear as well as 5 compressional wave transducers. The transducers were broadband with a central frequency of 1MHz (Panametrics V103RM for P-waves and V153RM for S-waves). A pulse generator (Panametrics 5077PR) was used for generating square-shape waveforms to provide input excitation for the source transducers. The input signal has the duration of 0.25 microsecond with the repetition rate of 5 kHz and amplitude of 300 V. The data acquisition system recorded transmitted P- and S-waves. The total time required for waveform acquisition through all 9 transducers was 1 seconds (i.e. sampling rate of 1 Hz). The transducers were coupled to the surface of the specimens using oven-baked honey (Busy Bee Honey) as the coupling medium. The specimen assembly process was standardized to ensure repeatability of seismic measurements. First, the honey was dehydrated at 90°C for 90 minutes to reduce its water content. A thin adhesive plastic film was placed on the surface of the testing specimen to prevent penetration of the honey into the pores of the specimen. This procedure has been successfully used in previous work (Hedayat et al., 2012; Hedayat et al., 2014a-d; Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018b).

Fig. 4. Schematic of Ultrasonic Transducers.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of direct shear experiments conducted on a Gosford sandstone rock joint are presented in this section. First, the normal load was applied to the specimen and platens that hold the transducer. The normal load was held constant at 5 MPa throughout the duration of the test. Then, an increasing shear load was applied to the specimen through a constant rate of shear displacement ($V_{\text{shear}} = 8 \mu\text{m/s}$) until static shear failure occurred in the rock joint (at approximately 1 mm of shear displacement, see inset of Figure 5). After a run in distance of approximately 1.5 mm, we applied the shear stress through steps of constant rate of shear displacement over more than two orders of magnitude

of shear displacement rate, first increasing and then decreasing V_{shear} (see Figure 5, hollow and full circles respectively). During the test, we measured the shear stress, τ , as well as the amplitude, A , and velocity, V , of the transmitted P- and S- waves for nine transducers (Figure 4). Whenever the ultrasonic wave attributes are presented, the P- and S-waves are differentiated by ‘p’ and ‘s’ subscripts, respectively. When no subscript is used, the results apply to both P- and S- waves.

In section 3.1 we introduce the observed mechanical response and their corresponding steady state values. In sections 3.2 and 3.3 we correlate the mechanical and geophysical measurements obtained when shearing the rock joint after the run in process during the increasing portion of the velocity step protocol. Results are shown in Figure 6, 7 and 8. In sections 3.4 and 3.5 we interpret Figure 5 in terms of the concepts previously developed.

Fig. 5. Steady state shear stress as function of shear displacement rate. Hollow circles show the values of steady state shear stress for increasing shear displacement rates and filled circles show the steady state shear stress for decreasing shear displacement rates. The lines with arrows show the sequence of shear displacement rate application. Error bars represent the average width of the stress drop in the stick-slip cycles. Inset: Shear stress as a function of the applied shear displacement.

3.1. Stable vs. unstable sliding

Our experiments show stable sliding at low shearing rates and unstable sliding at high shearing rates, see top panels of Figures 6 and 7 respectively. For smooth stable sliding conditions, after a given transient, the sliding velocity equals the applied shear displacement rate, V_{shear} , and the steady state value of the shear stress, τ_{ss} , equals the applied shear stress. For example, in the top panel of Figure 6, τ_{ss} is measured as the time average of τ at the end of each time interval, delimited by grey vertical lines. In contrast, during unstable sliding, see Figure 7, τ_{ss} is not well defined. In such conditions, the interface slips within a range of sliding velocities, changing between a static/sticking phase and a fast sliding phase. This unstable sliding generally shows periodic behavior and is called stick-slip. When sticking, for an elastic load imposing constant shear

displacement rate, we expect τ to linearly increase with time. When the shear load reaches the average shear strength of the interface (static threshold, τ^{th}), slip begins and the stresses decrease up to a minimum value, τ_{min} , where the interface sticks again, i.e. stick-slip cycles are characterized by a stress drop, $\Delta\tau = \tau^{\text{th}} - \tau_{\text{min}}$. Whenever we observe stick-slip sliding, we average $(\tau^{\text{th}} + \tau_{\text{min}})/2$ over several cycles to compare it with the true steady state values of the shear stress for smooth sliding conditions, and show the mean value of $\Delta\tau$ over several cycles with an error bar.

In Figure 5 we plot τ_{ss} as a function of V_{shear} for the full cycle of velocity steps applied. After discussing analyzing the acoustic measurements in the following two sections, we will discuss the shape of τ_{ss} vs. V_{shear} as well as the observed difference when increasing and decreasing V_{shear} .

3.2. Transmitted wave amplitude: local sensitivity to velocity-dependent mechanisms

In this section we discuss different mechanisms detected simultaneously and locally by the transmitted P- and S- wave amplitudes, present in both stable and unstable sliding conditions.

(a) Smooth sliding at low shearing rates

During a smooth velocity-strengthening (VS) frictional response, we observe that the transmitted P- and S- wave amplitudes have different dependence on V_{shear} (Figure 6). This shows that A_p and A_s are related to different mechanisms occurring at the interface.

Aging/healing mechanisms present at a frictional interface increase the shear response as sliding velocity decreases. The idea is that the lower the shearing rate, the more time the relaxation mechanisms have to develop and strengthen the interface, i.e. the interface ages or heals with increasing contact time or with low velocities. The typical example of a healing mechanism is perpendicular plastic creep, which increases the contact area as the system relaxes. Also, the formation of capillary bridges or atomic bonds may strengthen the interface with time of contact.

The amplitude of the transmitted compressional wave, A_p , is expected to increase with the area of contact in the region measured by the transducer. Since A_p decreases with V_{shear} , we associate A_p to be strongly related to healing mechanisms affecting the real contact area, specially considering that the incident waves are perpendicular to the rock joint. In contrast, the amplitude of the transmitted shear wave, A_s , increases with V_{shear} , as expected for the local shear strength of the interface. This VS response is typically associated to thermally activated and shear-induced creep of frictional contacts. The authors have recently introduced a rate and state model of frictional interfaces based on the interplay between creep flow and finite aging (Aragón et al., 2018). A relevant

aspect of the model is that the aging processes may still be present in the VS region of the curves for τ_{ss} vs. V_{shear} , as observed in this work. The model predicts that for sufficiently small velocities, A_p should become velocity independent, i.e. the contact area saturates at its maximum value.

The trends previously described, namely A_p (A_s) decreases (increases) with V_{shear} , are maintained when the shear displacement rate is both increased and decreased, as observed in the time sequence shown in Figure 6. The fact that these changes in A_p and A_s are different in magnitude for different transducers indicate that transducers have locally a different area of contact, ratifying the inhomogeneous structure of the contact area across the joint.

Fig. 6. Time dependence of the shear stress, τ , and amplitude and velocity of the P- and S- waves for rates of shear displacement, V_{shear} , indicated in the top panel. Grey vertical lines indicate velocity steps. Different colors indicate different transducers.

(b) Stick-slip cycles at high shearing rates

Figure 7 shows the zoomed-in version of the shear stress, and transmitted amplitude of P- and S- transducers during seven stick-slip cycles when

shearing at constant displacement rate, $V_{shear} = 8 \mu\text{m/s}$. Three types of periodic functions are observed to characterize the stick-slip behavior: (1) τ shows single frequency oscillations; (2) A_p shows sudden drops after a slow increase; and (3) A_s shows saw-tooth behavior. The observed oscillations in τ , instead of sharp drops, are originated in inertial effects of the measuring system. The increase of A_p during the stick-phase of the cycle strongly supports the existence of aging mechanisms, which locally grow the contact area. Moreover, the negative curvature of A_p as function of contact time is consistent with the expected logarithmic time increase of the aging processes. In the slip phase, the contact area drops fast and causes the observed sharp drop in A_p . The increase of A_s during the slip phase is consistent with the observed velocity strengthening of A_s during smooth sliding conditions, since during the slip phase the velocity increases from zero overpassing V_{shear} . This supports the idea that A_s measures a different physical process than A_p .

Fig. 7. Stick-slip cycles observed for the shear stress τ and for the amplitude of the transmitted P- and S- waves when shearing at constant displacement rate of $8 \mu\text{m/s}$. Top panel: the stress drop $\Delta\tau = 1.5 \text{ MPa}$.

3.3. Transmitted wave velocity: global sensitivity to the aperture of the joint

The contacting surfaces are well-mated prior to the test but gouge materials between the contact surfaces are observed after the experiment. In this section we relate changes in the transmitted P- and S- wave velocity, V , to global changes in the aperture of the joint, which we correlate to the formation and degradation of gouge during slippage. We conclude that when shearing at low rates the gouge expands and compacts, while most

of the observed gouge material is formed at higher velocities resulting in a net increase in the aperture of the joint.

(a) *Gouge formation/degradation at low shearing rates*

When shearing at low rates (VS region of Figure 5), we observe that equivalent simultaneous changes of V_p and V_s occur on all transducers, uncorrelated with changes in the shear stress. This indicates that for low V_{shear} values, some microphysical properties of the interface change simultaneously across the rock joint. A possible explanation is that the observed changes in wave velocity are because of the changes in the aperture (mean vertical distance between the two surfaces). These changes in the wave velocities can be either smooth or abrupt and positive or negative, and might be related to the formation, degradation or rearrangement of small debris as well as changes in the stiffness of the interface (Scuderi et al 2016). Also, the fact that the changes in the wave velocities are not correlated with the changes in τ indicate that in this velocity regime, material degradation (wear) does not depend on sliding velocity.

(b) *Gouge formation at high shearing rates*

Figure 8 shows a time sequence for the shear stress and the smoothed data using Bézier fits for amplitude and velocity of ultrasonic waves ($\langle A \rangle$ and $\langle V \rangle$ respectively) for different velocity steps. The largest changes in $\langle A \rangle$ and $\langle V \rangle$ are observed at higher velocities (VW region of Figure 5). If we expect the gouge at the joint to influence the frictional contacts, then the maximum changes in the transmitted wave attributes, e.g. $\langle A \rangle$ and $\langle V \rangle$, should occur when most of the gouge is formed, i.e. at high velocities.

A high fraction (7/9) of transducers show that $\langle V \rangle$ significantly increases for high shear displacement rates. Scuderi et al., 2016 showed that V_p decreases with compaction measured during the stick-slip cycle of gouge interfaces. This is consistent with the observed increase in $\langle V \rangle$ at high V_{shear} , indicating that the interface height expands as gouge is form. We therefore expect the contact area and the mean shear response, τ , to decrease with gouge formation at high V_{shear} . As shown in Figure 5, and discussed in Section 3.5, τ decreases after imposing the highest shear displacement rate of $30\mu\text{m/s}$ during 35 seconds. Even though the overall area of contact is expected to decrease, local variations may exist. Indeed, we observe that $\langle A \rangle$ (correlated to the contact area in the region measured by the transducer) both increases or decreases for different transducers.

The high fraction of transducers showing correlated results in $\langle V \rangle$ (as observed for instantaneous values of V in the VS regime shown in Figure 6), gives strong support to the hypotheses that V is sensitive to the mean aperture of the interface, since gouge material formed in a given region influence the aperture of the

whole rock joint. Local comminution or accumulation of smaller particles may lead to local compaction and might be the reason for some transducers to show a decrease in $\langle V \rangle$ while all others increase.

Fig. 8. Time dependence of the shear stress τ and amplitude and velocity of the P- and S- waves (smoothened by the Bézier fit) for different shear velocities, V_{shear} , as indicated in the top panel. Grey vertical lines indicate velocity steps and colored lines indicate different transducers. Figure 6 corresponds to this same time sequence in the interval [350:750] s.

3.4. *Velocity dependent friction*

As shown in Figure 5, we observe a maximum in τ_{ss} as function of V_{shear} . At low sliding velocities, we observe velocity-strengthening behavior (VS), where τ_{ss} slightly increases with V_{shear} and shows stable, smooth sliding. At higher velocities we observe velocity-weakening (VW), i.e. τ_{ss} decreases with V_{shear} . VW regions are characteristic of unstable sliding, since a small perturbation increasing the velocity decreases the shear response and consequently the system accelerates. We indeed observe stick-slip oscillations in this regime (Figure 7). A local maximum in τ_{ss} vs. V_{shear} curves similar to the one in Figure 5 has also been observed in shear experiments on Halite (Noda

and Shimamoto, 2010) and were related to material flow at low velocities and frictional unstable sliding at higher velocities. Very recently, a novel rate and state model of frictional interfaces has been presented, where the competition between VS and VW mechanisms result in such maximum in τ_{ss} (Aragón et al., 2018). According to this model, the global VS frictional response at low velocities is due to the VS dependence of thermally activated creep. Healing processes generate a VW region at higher velocities when the time scales of the relaxations involved are shorter and their contribution to the shear resistance diminishes. As described in Section 3.2, using ultrasonic measurements, we indeed detect two mechanisms acting simultaneously at the frictional interface with opposite velocity dependence.

3.5. Memory effects and state dependent friction

We observe that steady state friction, τ_{ss} , strongly depends on the sliding history. For example, there is a hysteretic behavior for τ_{ss} when a cycle of velocity steps is applied, first increasing and then decreasing V_{shear} (see Figure 5). This is also referred to as a memory effect, which implies that τ_{ss} is not only a function of the instantaneous velocity but also of its history. The rate and state friction laws (e.g. Nagata et al., 2012; Aragón et al., 2018) model this memory effects by incorporating state variables, which account for the effect of different physical mechanisms on the mean state of contact of the frictional interface. One such mechanism present in our experiment is the formation of gouge material in between the sliding surfaces (Section 3.3).

We next describe how we interpret the formation/degradation of gouge material as the process controlling the state of contact between the shearing surfaces, leading to state strengthening or weakening of the joint depending on the shearing rate.

(a) State weakening at high shearing rates

As discussed in Section 3.3b, most of the gouge material is formed during the highest shearing velocity of $V_{shear} = 30 \mu\text{m/s}$ with the maximum shear displacement of $\Delta X = V_{shear} \times 35 \text{ s} \approx 1\text{mm}$ (see the inset in Figure 5). A possible explanation for the weakening observed after sliding at $30\mu\text{m/s}$ (yellow curve is below the black curve in Figure 5) is that the generated gouge increases significantly the mean distance between the sliding surfaces (aperture), decreasing the contact area and the overall shear response. Therefore, we associate this weakening of the interface to a state variable describing the evolution of the contact area. Indeed, in Figure 8 we observe that 3 out of 5 sensors show that A_p decreases when entering the VW region at high shearing rates.

(b) State strengthening at low shearing rates

For low sliding velocities, we expect gouge material to be formed in small quantities and particle sizes. Its effect on the state of contact is opposite and less

pronounced compared to the effect of gouge formation at high velocities, i.e. it slightly strengthens the interface. This is observed in the top panel of Figure 6, which shows the changes in the applied shear stress for different shear displacement rates within the velocity-strengthening (VS) region of Figure 5. When the same shearing rate of $V_{shear} = 0.8 \mu\text{m/s}$ is applied to the rock joint, at the beginning and at the end of several velocity steps, with lower rates in between, τ_{ss} slightly increases (τ_{ss} in the first time interval is lower than τ_{ss} in the last time interval). This memory effect at low velocities is also observed for the amplitude of transmitted P- and S-waves (sensors 5P, 9P, 4S and 8S in Figure 6). The fact that sensors 5P and 9P show that A_p decreases, means that the state variable associated to the contact area would lower the overall steady state friction. Therefore, we infer that the observed mechanical strengthening of the interface with sliding is not related to an increase in the number of contacts or contact sizes, but related to processes affecting the shear strength, e.g. the formation of capillary bridges around new small particles or the formation of strong stress chains due to the angular shape of the newly formed particles (Yamashita et al., 2014). Indeed, we observe that sensors 8S and 4S show an increase in A_s , i.e. the state variable affecting the shear strength increases.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Novel shear experiments were performed to investigate the coupled mechanical-geophysical behavior of two blocks of Gosford sandstone (shaly type) with well-mated contact surfaces. The rock joint was loaded in a direct shear apparatus at different shearing rates (steps of constant shear displacement rate between $0.1 \mu\text{m/s}$ and $30 \mu\text{m/s}$) and fixed normal stress (5 MPa). During each stage of shearing, spatial variations of the ultrasonic compressional, P- and shear, S- wave attributes were recorded with nine pairs of source-receiver transducers placed at the sides of the specimen. Ultrasonic measurements provide spatially local information of the changes in the microphysical processes occurring at the interface and mechanical measurements provide average information on the frictional resistance.

We relate changes in the wave velocity, V , to changes in the aperture of the joint since they present high correlation between the transducers. Also, since the incident waves are perpendicular to the joint, we expect the amplitude of the transmitted P- wave, A_p , to be exclusively related to mechanisms affecting the contact area. In addition, we relate the amplitude of the transmitted S- waves, A_s , to mechanisms acting parallel to the shear direction. Comparing the simultaneous evolution of V , A_p and A_s for different shearing rates and sliding history, we conclude that gouge formation and comminution during sliding are responsible for the observed frictional dynamics, as summarized below.

When increasing the shearing rate, we observe a transition in the frictional response from velocity-strengthening (VS) to velocity-weakening (VW) sliding regimes, characterized by stable sliding and oscillatory stick-slip, respectively. In both regimes, A_p and A_s have opposite velocity dependence. A_p decreases with sliding velocity and increases during the sticking phase of the stick-slip cycle, as expected for healing processes occurring at the interface. In contrast, A_s increases with sliding velocity during steady state sliding and during the slip phase of the stick-slip cycle. The interplay between these processes, displaying VW and VS respectively, explain the observed local maximum in the measured steady state shear response as function of the applied shear displacement rate.

We observe that the frictional resistance is highly correlated with the sliding history. We qualitatively describe this memory effects within the rate and state framework. Our experiments may be described by two state variables. The first state variable is related to the contact area which significantly changes at high shearing rates when most of the gouge is formed. The second state variable is related to the local shear strength. It evolves at low shear displacement rates, where only small amounts of debris are formed or gouge comminution takes place. These processes slightly strengthen the interface, for example through capillary condensation since the small particles create new nucleation regions.

In summary, simultaneous evaluation of compressional P- and shear S- wave attributes (peak-to-peak amplitude and wave velocity) have shown to be a useful non-destructive technique to measure the state of contact and relate the frictional properties to microphysical processes occurring along the rock joints.

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